

OBSERVATIONS ON THE ANTERIOR PITUITARY-LIKE GONADOTROPIC HORMONE FROM THE HUMAN URINE OF PREGNANCY. PART I.

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The anterior pituitary-like gonadotropic hormone from pregnancy urine has been concentrated. The most concentrated preparation contains nitrogen (6.89%), carbohydrate (6.68%) and tyrosin (2.20%). It gives negative Millon's, Molisch and Fehlings tests but positive xanthoproteic and orcinol-sulphuric acid tests. It is stable below p_{H} 5.6 at 10° . It is partially inactivated by H_2S and H_2O_2 .

The presence of a sex-hormone in the urine of pregnancy, which is different from follicular and luteal hormones and resembles the hormone of the anterior lobe of the pituitary gland, which influences the gonads both in the male and in the female, was first indicated by Aschheim and Zondek (*Klin. Woch.*, 1928, 7, 1401). It has been called the anterior pituitary-like gonadotropic hormone of pregnancy urine, as it appears to resemble but is not identical with the hormone of the anterior pituitary body itself. The hormone preparation from pregnancy urine has been extensively used in medical therapy. Its chemical isolation, however, has not yet been possible and until this is done many biochemical questions particularly those of interaction between the different sex-hormones will remain unexplored. This paper deals with attempts at the concentration of this substance with a view to its eventual isolation. Several workers (Van Dyke and Lawrence, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1931, 43, 93; Dickens, *Biochem. J.*, 1930, 24, 1507; Fishcher and Ertol, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1931, 202, 83; Reiss and Haurowitz, *Z. exp. Med.*, 1929, 68, 371; Funk and Zeifrow, *Biochem. J.*, 1932, 28, 619; Katzman and Doisy, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1932, 98, 739; Zondek *et al.*, *Biochem. Z.*, 1933, 258, 102) have also attempted to concentrate this hormone and their efforts have been attended with a partial measure of success.

Our method involves the separation of the active substance by the adsorption of the material on benzoic acid followed by the removal of benzoic acid by treatment with cold acetone as suggested by Funk and Zeifrow (*loc. cit.*) and Katzman and Doisy (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Seven litres of human urine of late pregnancy were collected in a glass jar surrounded by ice and preserved at 0° for 36 hours. The p_{H} of the

cold urine was adjusted to 4.3 by means of glacial acetic acid. It was centrifuged and the clear supernatant liquid was transferred to a glass vessel immersed in ice. While stirring it with a mechanical stirrer, 530 c.c. of acetone saturated with benzoic acid (room temperature 30°) were gradually added to the liquid in the vessel. The precipitated benzoic acid absorbate was filtered under suction and thoroughly washed with 200 c.c. of a saturated aqueous solution of benzoic acid. It was then treated with 530 c.c. of cold acetone (10°), filtered and washed with another 100 c.c. of cold acetone. It was dried overnight in a vacuum desiccator (10°) over CaCl₂ and triturated with 50 c.c. of water in a glass mortar. The active material was eluted by 0.05N-NaOH by adjusting the p_H to 9.6. In order to avoid the destruction of the activity of the substance in alkaline medium the p_H of the substance was quickly readjusted to 7.0 by means of acetic acid. The syrupy solution was centrifuged, the precipitate was twice washed with water and the washings were added to the centrifugate. The solution was made up to 75 c.c. and treated with 750 c.c. of cold acetone (10°). Minute particles of a white precipitate settled at the bottom when kept for 25 minutes at 10°. This precipitate was separated and dried over CaCl₂ in a vacuum desiccator. A brownish scale-like substance (0.6 g.) was obtained.

Biological Assay.

Immature female albino rats weighing between 30 g. and 42 g. were taken for testing the active substance. The animals were kept on normal diet consisting of milk, brown bread and whole wheat. A solution containing 0.24 mg. of the concentrated material per c.c. was kept in a cold store (10°). A daily dose of 0.3 c.c. of this solution was injected intraperitoneally into each animal. A group of 4 animals was treated with this solution for 5 days. It was observed that the vagina of the four controls remained closed whereas that of all the treated animals opened before the 5th day after the first dose was injected into the animals. On the 6th day the vaginal smears of all the animals were tested. The serous smear of the treated animals took 0.5% eosine stain. There were non-nucleated cornified squamous cells associated with leucocytes and red blood cells. The mucoid smear of the controls did not give the positive maturation test in the vaginal smear. There was a distinct enlargement of the ovaries and uteri of the treated animals as is observed from Table I given below.

Effect of the Change of p_H on the Biological Activity of the Substance.

A solution containing 0.24 mg. of the active material per c.c. was adjusted to three different p_H values by means of diluted hydrochloric

acid and sodium hydroxide. The solutions were kept at 10°. The activity was tested as described above. The ovaries of all the animals as well as the uteri were separated and the mean weight of each group was taken. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

p_H	No. of animals	Mean body wt. of the animals.	Mean wt. of the ovaries and uteri.	Mean weight of the ovaries & uteri per g. of the mean body wt.
3·6	4	35 g.	126 mg.	3·6 mg.
5·6	4	35	88	2·5
8·6	4	34	96	2·8
(untreated controls)	3	38	75	1·9

From Table I it appears that the substance is fairly stable within the range of p_H 3·6 to 8·6.

Electrodialysis.

A solution containing 3 mg. of the active extract per c.c. was divided into three portions and the p_H of the solutions was adjusted to three different values : (a) 3·6 (b) 6·6 and (c) 8·6 by means of glacial acetic acid and sodium hydroxide.

(1) To 10 c.c. of the solution (a) 5 c.c. of phosphate-citrate buffer of p_H 3·6 were added.

(2) To 10 c.c. of the solution (b) 5 c.c. of phosphate buffer of p_H 6·6 were added.

(3) To 10 c.c. of the sample (c) 5 c.c. of phosphate buffer of p_H 8·6 were added.

All the three samples (1), (2) and (3) were electro-dialysed in a cold store (4°) for 4 hours at 220 volts and 9 milli amp. An agar-agar bridge of 2% agar-agar with 2% sodium chloride and parchment paper were used. In order to maintain a steady current of 9 milli amp. the concentration of the buffer of the side-chamber of the dialyser was different from that of the central chamber although other factors of the experiment were constant. For p_H 3·6, p_H 6·6 and p_H 8·6, the buffer for the side-chambers was diluted 20 times, 10 times, and 7 times respectively. Testing the solutions in the different compartments showed that the active material was not dialysable through parchment paper within the p_H range studied.

Further Concentration of the Active Material.

In connection with the above experiments it was observed that the solution of the active substance gave a precipitate when the p_H was adjusted to 3.6 by means of glacial acetic acid. 10 C.c. of the solution containing 0.24 mg. of the active material per c.c. were, therefore, adjusted to p_H 3.6 by means of glacial acetic acid and the mixture centrifuged. The clear centrifugate (A) was found to be active. The precipitate was treated with 10 c.c. of water, and the p_H adjusted to 6.8 by means of sodium hydroxide. This was found to be inactive (Table II).

TABLE II.

Substance	Total solid material injected.	Number of animals.	Mean body weight.	Mean weight of the ovaries and uteri.	Mean wt. of the ovaries & uteri per g. of mean body wt
Centrifugate at p_H 3.6 (A)	0.096 mg.	3	35 g.	145 mg.	4.1 mg.
Precipitate from (A) dissolved at p_H 6.8	0.140	3	34	71	2.1
Untreated controls		3	39	86	2.2

Table II shows that none of the active material is precipitated by glacial acetic acid at p_H 3.6. It was also found that about 59% of the inactive solids were eliminated by this process.

When a concentrated syrupy solution of the extract containing 20 mg. of the crude substance was adjusted to p_H 3.6 by means of glacial acetic acid a precipitate, as stated above, was formed. This was centrifuged off and the clear liquid was treated with 10 times its volume of cold acetone (12°). A white precipitate was obtained which was filtered under suction and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 (10°). An amorphous white hygroscopic powder was obtained, which was about 41% of the original crude substance. This acetone-precipitated active material contained about 60% of the original active material.

Effect of H_2S and H_2O_2 on the Centrifugate (A) at p_H 3.6.

The samples of the centrifugate (A) at p_H 3.6 were treated separately with H_2S and H_2O_2 .

(a) H_2S was passed for 5 minutes into 5 c.c. of the solution and then removed completely by CO_2 .

(b) Three drops of 30% H_2O_2 were added to 5 c.c. of the solution.

(c) A sample of the solution was kept as a positive control.

These were biologically tested and the results are shown in Table III. The effect of the centrifugate was taken as 100 and of the treated fractions as percentages of this.

TABLE III.

Number of animals	Solution treated by	Activity.
3	Untreated active solution	100
3	H_2O_2	75
3	H_2S	67
3 (untreated controls)	—	0

Stability of the Centrifugate (A) at 10°.

The solid substance was found to remain active for a long time. But the whole of activity was lost within 8 days when the substance was kept without any buffer in an aqueous solution and the p_H of the solution was between 5.6 and 8.6 at 10°. The alteration of the p_H during the same time is shown in Table IV, which would indicate that the loss of activity from p_H 5.6 upwards is accompanied by a shift of p_H .

TABLE IV.

From p_H		to p_H .
3.6	...	3.6
5.6	...	5.4
7.2	...	6.2
8.6	...	6.6

Different Chemical Tests.

The active material obtained before treatment with glacial acetic acid did not give any positive Molisch, Millon's or Fehling's test, nor did it give any precipitate with phosphotungstic or trichloroacetic acid. It gave a precipitate readily with lead acetate, mercuric chloride and acetone. Definite xanthoproteic and orcinol-sulphuric acid tests were, however, obtained.

Analytical Results of the Purified Substance.

The purified material obtained by acetone precipitation was found to contain 6.89% of N, whereas the crude substance obtained by the simple adsorption of the active substance on benzoic acid contained 12.08% N. The purified material contained 6.68% of carbohydrate as estimated by the orcinol-sulphuric acid method of Sorensen and Haugaard (*Biochem Z.*, 1933, 260, 619) as improved by Kondo and Muragama (*J. Agr. Chem. Soc., Japan* 1937, 13, 473). The tyrosine content of the substance was determined by Wu's method using the phenol reagent and found to be 2.20%. It may be mentioned that the carbohydrate content of our preparation was comparable with the carbohydrate content (6.0%) of the gonadotropic preparation obtained from the anterior pituitary by Hartzman and Bens (*Nature*, 1938, 142, 115) and it was considerably less than the value 19.0% found by the same authors (*loc. cit.*) for the substance obtained from pregnancy urine.

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